

INNOVATIVE KNOWLEDGE, LEADING NEW GENERATION. ALBANIAN UNIVERSITIES -STUDY CASE

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is figure out that the challenges posed by COVID-19 will empower the education and teacher profession and will uplift it for the growth of the Nations both economically and intellectually. Education and teaching Profession will become progressive, flexible, multidisciplinary and technology & skill-focused which will redefine learning in Albania and shape up more ethical learners.

In these challenging times, teaching as a profession has undergone a paradigm shift and so have the Methodology and Pedagogy of teaching. To keep up the pace with the changing needs of the world and modern tools of teaching, teachers are skilling, up skilling, and reskilling to remain relevant in the coming times and contribute towards building the nation. With current technological advancements, education is made easily available & accessible to the remotest local globally.

Distance learning, e-learning, multi-disciplinary learning all form new pillars of the education system, panning a great scope of professional growth for teaching aspirants. Virtual learning too has opened up multiple avenues for the teaching profession without limiting its scope of work to any geographical boundaries. This has also opened up the doors to global platforms and given multi-dimensional exposure with better earnings and better learning.

It's hard to predict the future, not because you do not have the goal for it or the forces to achieve it but for the simple fact that the *FUTURE itself is a unknown territory that you have never stepped on it.*

Education, teaching is a noble profession. It may not require the same skillsets as other noble professions like being a doctor, but it is a noble vocation. For many educators, they were called into it. But with the pandemic crippling all sense of normalcy all over the world, which includes the closure, both temporarily and permanently, of many schools, the teaching profession has also suffered. And this is a profession that has **long been suffering** in not just during the crisis, teaching has always been one of the noblest professions, and the teachers have always been a catalyst for social and behavioral changes. Teachers by their Knowledge, wisdom, patience, etc. have nurtured the young minds and shaped their personalities and career and will play a crucial role through every life period.

With structural policy reforms, the role of teachers has a good scope to grow and foster. Other professional jobs might gain importance but teaching shall always remain a noble career which has the power to change billions of lives.

Key words: education, challenge, future technology, role, personality, inspiration.

Introduction

The main purpose in this referral is the way how to develop knowledge independently from the students themselves, which the key of success based on knowledge given by the professor (or leader in our case), which permits students creating sense of leadership. The preparation of human products from the university requires a new philosophy of learning, which means; combining traditional learning with analytical one, critical and creative learning, where teaching, education and professors (leader)+ students are forming an undistinguishable triangle.

The basis of their intellectual development is a responsibility of the university in essence, should provide adequate knowledge including student self-knowledge. Even in the cases of high level of pedagogical knowledge(or leadership mission), it cannot fully achieve its goals if the students do not create intellectual expressive habits, in order to work every day, and not simply to reproduce, but to process information creatively, to analyze-verify and to implement it.(including practice in real life)

As the matter of fact Education remains the foundation of knowledge and culture, which will and should cultivate intellectual skills and abilities for critical and analytical learning (1) Unfortunately, not only learning, but also passive thinking, reproductive and mechanical thinking, it is cultivated in kindergarten or childhood, and also in university, and consequently follows a profession as a specialist of every field: teacher-leader, economist, doctor, lawyer, politician etc.

Life in itself is another school that never stops teaching new things and phenomena. Practice can stimulate and fasten the critical thinking, but the efficiency, is not too small (especially with students where the opportunities are greater)

Being successful in the exam means not only acquiring knowledge, but above all, to be able to transform the acquired knowledge into a useful product. This phenomena is called "learning by doing".

On one hand the school has been and remains the teaching and cultural institution that gives solid, organized and systematic knowledge. On the other hand, it is the school that has also had and has more conservatism. It has been quite formalized and has also had frozen pedagogical structure! To err is human but in our case is wrong that these phenomena are not ONLY related to the work of the lecturer and the university, but I Think it is related to school in general. The Strike is straightforward.

There is something to be noticed, in Albanian Universities exist the prevalence of reproductive learning which limits the creative activity to the primitive and infantile stage. In this way it solidifies and standardizes thinking, nourishes scholarship, dogmatism, and even conformism. Such academic system does not give opportunity for self-conscious attitude and persuasive convenience through proofs, confrontation, and discussions that is required for the recognition of truth.

And what is else to be noted? Is that the students carry the fruits of this learning for a long time in life and work? Personally I DOUBT.

Later on, student start using brain power.

Hypotheses And Research Question

The education responsibility of student formation is extended enough to achieving the good results during the exam. The perception and students' experience on scientific knowledge are often not taken into consideration. In addition, in front of the logical questions, most students are not able to defend or reject a statement at a time when they remember many theories and formulas, so they cannot distinguish what is essential, as they reproduce entire pages of the book.

It is not enough to stay attached to the problem, but to make a face-to-face and radical confrontation, escalated over time, of the old conception and practices combined with searching for new ways, forms and methods, embodied to the problems that require solutions.

The chart 1 below shows student's development.

As is shown in the chart 1 which is being analyzed through recent years in Vlora University, Albania and it is shown that about 20 % to 25 % of the students gain knowledge through Listening the lecture and the rest remain to be gained in real practice and in Daily Life.

Also many researches has shown that students develop thinking skills more effectively, if they are currently involved with practical forms while they are studying. But these researches and developments are valid when are presently applied.

In the field of education through theory and scientific research many innovations for education at all levels of education, and has often failed to implement these innovations. Still in nowadays the method where the lecturer (leader) speak and students listen dominate at the universities auditorium. It is important not only to recognize the nature and strategies of active learning, but

also the usual barriers and barriers that increase the resistance of pedagogues to realistically implement these strategies.

H-1 (hypothesis). Education as a process must encourage an active, continuing communication of concerns, observations, data, insights and suggestions from the Professor (leader) among students themselves.

What will make things different in 21-st century is that the world is going through a transformation that effects industrial word as well as social, political and economic one. The world is being fundamentally reshaped by the information and technology. (Collin Powell “The leadership secrets of Collin Powell ’pp 37 -38, published in USA 2002 by Oren Harari and R.R.Donnely)

According to Traditional learning, the student is seen to be fulfilled with knowledge. But knowledge is not static and students should not be seen as passive part in acquiring knowledge but as an active part of creating their background. They must actively participate in the learning process.

The student assisted by professor as a Leader is consistently involved in tasks to a high level of thinking; to analyze, to synthesize, to evaluate by creating their own beliefs on what they think. These useful connection makes up the building of knowledge. When students work in groups and do activities, in order to increase reflective thinking about what they are doing; then he/she (students ‘themselves) will to be able to use the knowledge gained in resolving problem situations in life and society. The pedagogue as a Leader has the purpose of structuring, orienting, guiding and analyzing ideas.

The professor as a leader will thus guide the modeling and intellectual formation of the most responsive students for their task accomplishment. This requires that professor as a leader should have

- a) Personally trained,
- b) Scientifically,
- c) Methodologically and
- d) Didactically.

It is important to consider what the student is having on his head, without seeing as a duty filling their head.

Methodology

The projects were implemented in order to test knowledge taken and students’ creativity and critical thinking. The methodology used is that of observation and testing students by the projects that we as professor as a leader have planned with the groups of students in University of Vlora, specifically students of Department of foreign Languages.

Recent researches has shown that students develop thinking skills more effectively if they are currently involved with the materials they are studying!

What is taken into consideration? Students reaction and their effective product in lecturing-observations in real time; Constructive Theory of education& leading experiences.

According to David Kolb, learning is seen as a combination of learning from a concrete experiences, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization and active experimentation, which follow each other according to a closed cycle shown.

In this cycle it can be started at any point, but the next steps follow the cycle again.

Constructing functional and coherent scientific models occurs spontaneously for most students. Making to work the mechanism of this cycle, it involves students inevitably in the activities of thinking and acting. They must perform various activities that help to build functional models

In order for students to succeed, they should increase their confidence in their ability to learn and to process all the scientific information In and Out of the Class. Duties and their continuous assessment will force students to take their role by not staying passive. Education -Active learning methods that integrate thinking into action have two important goals:

a)make the class more dynamic b) the student is not just a figure, but also a voice creating to the students intellectual skills, in order to work every day in daily life , c)do not only reproduce, to increase the way student process information in a creative way c)develops the way to implement it.

"If you want to shape and strengthen the mind of the student," Jean-Jacques Rousseau says, give them a chance to work, to be ready to act, to be constantly moving. And this is achieved by realizing from them an effort to write a report, essay or a simple memorization, an interpretation, a translation of a text or article, resolving an equation and practicing a sport.

To the same idea is Colin Powell to be successful, leaders must consciously work to stay in touch with the best ideas of the people that you lead, in our case the students.

So in order to answer, the key question is that also the process of involving people and making them taking responsibility for innovative and fresh ideas and strategies, for shaping of their ideas.

The success is depending on implementable ideas, if they are useful to humanity? ‘

My personal opinion in this case is that: A good professor (leader) has the substantial goal to inspire students not just to voice the problem, but also to *figure out* new ways.

Reflection and Results in daily education process!

The education process distinguishes a professional one from a non-professional one. In this way, they point out the need to ensure that approved training programs prepare members of the vocational profession, are capable of doing well in daily life;

The education stands out for:

- The professional responsibility and the power that the professor has in improving students' knowledge and life.
- The education as a unique professional experience that other professions have
- The basic establishment of not only professional but also as personal development.
- The aspirations and as a model that students create to guide them in future
- The right values to the dignity of the professors (Leader) profession

- The contributions in Albania and the support for the public interest, in improving teaching process.

For further development in Higher Education in University during such processes and effort of changes, PEOPLE can fail, in this case “Don’t punish for failure “ . Find ways not to make the same mistake twice, using sensible-effective tools and tactics.

1-Challenge the pros to get better solutions. Whether the situations is challenging you or your subordinate students is challenging you, remember that more opinion and more voices translates into more alternative opinion. This is particularly important when events are moving faster than your collective experience has prepared you for.

2-Emphasize, dignity, respect, and honor while disagreeing!

3-Be patient!

4- Built a setting in which all feel free to speak out

Learning should be active in function of constructing and developing knowledge and skills. But we often fall victim to the belief that what we explain to students is what they learn. Each person can dominate one of the styles more than others, or can use Different styles in several circumstances.

Others find themselves at the lowest level of the class and this certainly creates and strengthens the opinion that some are awake and some others are unable to recognize different learning styles and including different activities in accordance to characteristics, skills, and student experience individually or as a group.

This will increase the quality of learning for all students.

But learning styles do not have the effect on student achievement in different active learning environments. Students learn better when they are actively involved in this process. Studies have shown that we remember 20% of what we hear, 50% of what we see and 80% of what we do. We learn from experience, we learn in interaction with others, and with everything that surrounds us and we do it all the time since we were born. Without this combination, we would get less.

Lessons can be theoretical or practical, whether they involve thinking or acting. It is not enough just to learn new concepts and their theoretical development. It is not enough to act, as it is not enough just to think. Thinking through experience realizes connectivity through thinking and acting. In order for knowledge to be functional, students should know how and where to use this knowledge.

Conclusions

Many aspects of Higher Education, in particular the level of teaching and research in higher education institutions (HEI-s), do not respond to the dynamics of changes in Albanian society and its inclinations! The higher education system still does not sufficiently respond to the needs of the future of society and the economy of the country.

If we want to prepare the new generation to adapt to the change, we must focus NOT only on knowledge, but on the skills- WHAT WE CAN DO WITH OUR KNOWLEDGE? .

The factors influencing are not only individual experience, talents, competitive abilities, culture, social values associated with the student, but also they related to the school itself. The key factor is that academic-curricula should provide the opportunity to practice the knowledge taken at school in order to enrich students' experiences.

Another important factor is the new viewpoint of the triangle knowledge-student-professors where the professor (leader) leads students and students construct and develop knowledge by acting and doing. This not only in school but throughout life. The design of new figures to the student is made through the application of high intellectual abilities to achieve interpretation, analyzing, synthesizing and evaluating learning.

Sometimes, I blame the Information technology that makes us apathetic but it also provides opportunities for rapid and adaptable change. There are many ways to reform the teaching process, but all require changing the concepts of learning by integrating thinking and acting, planning a clear and flexible program, implementing strategies and methods in line with the conditions and resources we have, the awareness of the students with the trade market in accordance with the personal and social perspective. In this way, to all students interested and motivated University offers them very good opportunities for a more productive career. Another important factor is the new philosophy of learning as a process that generates sustainable knowledge, values, emotions, feedback, creativity, self-action, leadership and management skills.

The Future is an unknown territory and the progress is sure to happen!

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